

INVESTIGATION OF THE PREVALENCE OF CYBERCHONDRIA AMONG TEACHERS REGARDING VARIOUS VARIABLES¹

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Abstract

Cyberchondria is a term that describes a condition in which health concerns and worries are increased by excessive information seeking on the internet. Cyberchondria is seen as a side effect of modern technology and the easy accessibility of information. This new problem, which is thought to affect every individual, may also affect teachers, who are the heroes of education, and in this respect, the prevalence of cyberchondria among teachers should be investigated. The aim of the study is to examine the cyberchondria levels of teachers from different branches according to various variables. The participants consisted of 345 teachers. A general survey method was used in the study. During the analysis, descriptive statistics, an independent sample t-test, and a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used. Analyses were carried out with the SPSS 23.0 statistical program. As a result of the findings, it was seen that the cyberchondria levels of the teachers were close to medium. In addition, there was no significant difference in terms of cyberchondria in terms of gender, marital status, educational status, having children status, having chronic disease, preferred device for internet use, and purpose of internet use variables. As a result of the findings obtained in the study, the subject of cyberchondria was discussed, and some examples were discussed.

Keywords: Cyberchondria, Anxiety, Teachers, Quantitative research

Introduction

The rapid spread of technology and the internet today has facilitated access to all kinds of information. This rapid development of information and communication technologies has facilitated access to all kinds of information and increased the research of individuals about health problems on the internet (Durak-Batıgün et al., 2018). Because individuals have had the opportunity to easily provide all kinds of information about their diseases and disorders from various health sites on the internet. Individuals become aware of the options related to their own health and the options they have are increasing (Mcdaid & Park, 2010). In addition, with the internet, individuals living in different geographies and having common health problems come together and support each other by sharing their health problems and the problems they experience with each other (Çınarlı, 2008). The reason for this can be attributed to the fact that health information is difficult to understand because it requires advanced language knowledge when there is no internet, but over time, this medical language has been reduced

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to a level that the society can understand with the internet, reducing the necessity of information obtained from the expert (Günler, 2015). As a result, the internet has many benefits in terms of healthy living and related information. Although the Internet provides benefits and convenience to individuals in this regard, it has some negative aspects in terms of health. For example, it is observed that anxiety and worry increase in some individuals as they conduct health-related research.

Nowadays, individuals exhibit the behaviour of searching for all kinds of health information to be learned from the internet when they get sick or when they suspect abnormal issues in their own bodies and when health personnel cannot be reached immediately (Demirhan & Eke, 2021). It is because of such behaviours that the concept of "cyberchondria" has emerged. Cyberchondria has been defined as people's excessive behaviour of repeatedly searching for health-related topics on the internet and, as a result, creating anxiety and worry (Starcevic & Berle, 2013). According to another definition, it is defined as excessive online health information-seeking behaviour upon reviewing one's own health status (McElroy & Shevlin, 2014). Recupero (2010) defined the concept of cyberchondria as the increased anxiety of individuals who use the Internet to search for health information in the face of the results they reach. Individuals suffering from cyberchondria may experience high stress due to the information about health problems and concepts related to their bodies that they can obtain because of excessive health research on the internet (Menon et al., 2020). It also shows that individuals have economic losses since they use health services more due to the anxiety that occurs in individuals (Crane, 2014; Uzun et al., 2017; Uzun & Zencir, 2018). The fact that people suffering from cyberchondria try to apply the wrong treatment methods as a result of the research they have done on the internet about their own diseases can also lead to some negative consequences. Cyberchondria can cause problems that may affect the social environment as well as medical and economic problems. The fact that the person repeatedly tells his/her health problems to his/her family members and close friends, and they must listen to them may lead to negative consequences, such as the close circle getting tired and tired. According to Yavuz (2017), people who suffer from cyberchondria may spend too much time on the internet about their diseases, spend too much time on the internet, cannot allocate enough time for their social relationships, and cause damage to their relationships. Since these people are usually away from their work environment due to issues related to their illnesses, they may also experience financial difficulties, which may cause problems in family relationships (Işıkdere, 2016). Similarly, the fact that individuals are busy with health problems during the day affects their focus on their work and causes them to leave incomplete work. This negatively affects work life (Tarhan et al., 2021). In this respect, studies on cyberchondria should be researched. In this study, it was aimed at investigating the prevalence of cyberchondria among teachers. The reason why teachers were selected as participants is that they are the most important stakeholders in education, and in negative situations that they may experience due to cyberchondria, the effect may be not only on themselves but also on their students in terms of education and training. In this context, answers to the following questions were sought:

1. What is the cyberchondria level of teachers?
2. Do the cyberchondria levels of teachers vary according to gender, marital status, educational status, having children status, having chronic disease, preferred device for internet use, and purpose of internet use?

Method

In this study, in which teachers' cyberchondria levels were examined in terms of various variables, the general survey method was used. Survey studies are studies that aim to describe the characteristics of the views of large masses (Büyüköztürk et al., 2016).

Participants

The participants consisted of 345 teachers from different branches working in public and private schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education currently operating in Türkiye. The participants were accessed through a convenience sampling method. Convenience sampling aims to eliminate the limitations that the researcher may experience in terms of time and to reach the most accessible people (Büyüköztürk et al., 2016). Labor, money and time problems play an important role in the selection of this method. An online questionnaire was used to collect data from teachers with the help of Google documents. 234 of the participants were female (%67.8) and 111 were male (%32.2). The average age was found to be approximately 29. Finally, teachers work in different branches, mostly in the Marmara region of Turkey (% 67). Demographic data for the teachers who participated in the study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Data pertaining to participants

Variables	Categories	N	%
Gender	Female	234	67.8
	Male	111	32.2
Marital Status	Married	219	63.5
	Single	126	36.5
Educational status	Bachelor's degree	229	66.4
	Master's degree	116	33.6
Having children status	Yes	198	57.4
	No	147	42.6
Having a chronic disease	Yes	44	12.8
	No	301	87.2
Preferred device for internet use	Laptop/PC	53	15.4
	Smartphone	292	84.6
Purpose of internet use	Social network sites	121	35.1
	Education and Information	105	30.4
	Communication	64	18.6
	Other (Gaming, Surf, News, Banking, Shopping)	55	15.9

Data Collection Tools

The data were collected through the Personal Information Form prepared by the researchers and the Cyberchondria Severity Scale-Short Form developed by Söyler et al. (2021).

Personal Information Form. The questions in the form are aimed at determining the gender, age, marital status, having children status, income level, education level, branch, having a chronic illness status, the device with which they usually use the Internet, and the purpose for which they use the Internet.

Cyberchondria Severity Scale Short Form. The scale was originally developed by McElroy et al. (2019) to measure the concerns and behaviours of individuals regarding the search for health information over the internet. The Turkish validity and reliability study was conducted by Söyler et al (2021). The scale A 5-point Likert-type was determined as Always (5) ..., Never (1). It was determined that there were no items to be reverse scored in the scale. In the scale consisting of 12 items, items 1, 3, and 6 measure the *excessiveness* sub-dimension, items 4, 8, and 9 measure the *distress* sub-dimension, items 5, 11, and 12 measure the *reassurance* sub-dimension, and items 2, 7, and 10 measure the *compulsion*

dimension. In the study, the Cronbach alpha coefficient for the whole scale was .86, .77 for the *excessiveness* sub-dimension, .78 for the *distress* sub-dimension, .74 for the *reassurance* sub-dimension, and .78 for the *compulsion* sub-dimension.

Data Collection Process and Analysis

The data collection process lasted for two months during August–September through an online questionnaire. Permission was obtained from the Trakya University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences Ethics Committee Commission for the study conducted on a voluntary basis (2023.03.04–03/04). To collect the data in the quantitative part of the study, firstly, the questions in the Personal Information Form and the items in the cyberchondria scale were digitized through the Google Forms application. After this process, the link created by the application was first shared with the teachers working in public and private schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education via the WhatsApp application, and then it was tried to reach the teachers by sharing on social media platforms such as Facebook, X, and Instagram. In addition, the link shared with teacher groups was filled in by the teachers in the groups and shared with other teachers outside the group. Teachers were informed about the questionnaire before data collection. The participants took approximately 15 minutes to answer the data collection tools. In the study, 373 teachers who volunteered and wanted to give their own answers were reached. However, as a result of the relevant analyses, the data of 28 participants with extreme values in terms of the scale and its sub-factors were excluded from the analysis. Thus, the number of participants was 345. To determine whether the data were normally distributed, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, one of the normality tests, was run first in the data analysis process. After the test, extreme values were eliminated, however it was observed that the information was not normally distributed. Thereupon, kurtosis and skewness values were analysed considering the number of data points (skewness = 0.427; kurtosis = -0.512). When the skewness and kurtosis values were analysed, it was seen that the values were in the range of -1.96 and +1.96, and it was accepted that the data were normally distributed (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). Therefore, parametric tests were used in the study. Thus, an independent sample t-test and a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were performed in this study.

Findings

As a result of the descriptive statistics carried out to obtain the cyberchondria levels of the teachers, it was determined that the average score obtained from the cyberchondria scale was $M=2.93$. When the sub-factors are analysed, it is seen that the "Excessiveness" sub-factor has a higher score than the other factors in terms of teachers' cyberchondria ($M=3.89$). Descriptive statistics of the scale and its sub-dimensions are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the scale and sub-dimensions

Scale and Sub-dimensions	N	Min.	Max.	M	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Cronbach Alfa
Cyberchondria	345	1.17	5,00	2.93	.734	-.066	-.440	.86
1. Excessiveness	345	1.67	5.00	3.89	.863	-.580	-.417	.77
2. Distress	345	1.00	5.00	3.01	1.011	-.135	-.562	.78
3. Reassurance	345	1.00	5.00	2.83	1.021	-.066	-.681	.74
4. Compulsion	345	1.00	5.00	2.01	.940	.804	-.143	.78

In the study, it was also examined whether the cyberchondria level of teachers differed in terms of gender. In this context, an independent sample t-test analysis was conducted. As a result of the findings, no difference was found in terms of gender ($p>.05$). The findings are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. *Independent samples t-test results according to gender*

Categories	N	M	Std. Dev.	t	df	p
Female	234	2.97	.743	1.195	343	.23
Male	111	2.87	.711			

The cyberchondria levels of teachers were also analysed in terms of marital status variable. An independent sample t-test was conducted to determine whether teachers' cyberchondria levels differed according to marital status. As a result of the findings, no difference was found according to marital status ($p > .05$). The findings obtained are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. *Independent samples t-test results according to marital status*

Categories	N	M	Std. Dev.	t	df	p
Married	219	2.92	.752	-.758	343	.45
Single	126	2.98	.702			

An independent samples t-test was conducted to determine whether the levels of the teachers changed according to their educational status. According to the findings, there was no difference between the cyberchondria groups according to educational status ($p > .05$). The findings obtained are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. *Independent samples t-test results according to educational level*

Categories	N	M	Std. Dev.	t	df	p
Bachelor's degree	219	2.96	.737	.796	343	.42
Master's degree	126	2.89	.728			

An independent samples t-test was conducted to examine whether teachers' levels of cyberchondria differed based on parental status (having children or not). The findings indicated that there was no significant difference in cyberchondria levels between teachers with and without children ($p > .05$). The detailed results of the analysis are presented in Table 6

Table 6. *Independent samples t-test results according to having children*

Categories	N	M	Std. Dev.	t	df	p
Yes	198	2.89	.742	-1.289	343	.20
No	147	3.00	.721			

To ascertain whether the teachers' levels of cyberchondria varied based on their chronic disease status, an independent samples t-test was performed. As a result of the findings, no significant difference was found ($p > 0.05$). The results of the analysis are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. *Independent samples t-test results according to having chronic disease*

Categories	N	M	Std. Dev.	t	df	p
Yes	44	3.07	.802	1.309	343	.19
No	301	2.91	.722			

An independent sample t-test was conducted to determine whether teachers' cyberchondria levels differed according to the technological device preferred for internet use. The results showed that there was no significant difference ($p > .05$). The results of the analysis are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. *Independent samples t-test results according to preferred device for internet use*

Categories	N	M	Std. Dev.	t	df	p
Computer (PC/Laptop)	53	2,82	.865	-1.204	343	.23
Smartphone	292	2.95	.707			

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine whether teachers' cyberchondria levels differed according to the purpose of internet use. As a result of the findings, it was seen that there was no difference between the groups separated according to the purposes ($p > .05$). The results of the analysis are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. *ANOVA results according to purposes of the internet use*

Categories	N	M	Std. Dev.	F	p
Social Network Sites	121	2.95	.688		
Education and Information Communication	105	2.96	.821	.182	.69
Other (Gaming, Surf, News, Banking, Shopping)	64	2.88	.637		
	55	2.91	.773		

Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, it was aimed at examining the cyberchondria levels of teachers according to various variables. In this context, teachers' cyberchondria level was determined as the first finding. According to the findings, the mean score of teachers' cyberchondria level was found to be $M = 2.89$. In terms of cyberchondria sub-dimensions, it was seen that the "excessiveness" sub-factor had a higher score than the other factors ($M = 3.89$). Consequently, the impact of excessiveness—that is, approaching doctors armed with knowledge gleaned from searching multiple websites and seeking advice—on the rise in the teachers' cyberchondria level is greater than that of the other sub-dimensions. When the related literature was analysed, there was no study conducted with teachers who constitute the target group of this study. Therefore, studies conducted with other participant groups are analysed in this section. In a study conducted with the participation of academicians, it was reported that the health anxiety levels of academicians were low. This result was attributed to the fact that the majority of academics did not have a chronic illness in the same study (Özyıldız & Alkan, 2022). Similarly, in a study conducted with the participation of nurses who interpreted the level of cyberchondria as below average, this situation was attributed to the fact that nurses have a better command of health knowledge than other individuals (Polat, 2020). Contrary to the findings of the study, there are also studies in which the level of cyberchondria is at a moderate level (Fergus, 2014; Kalmaz & Temel, 2024; Norr et al., 2015; Uzun, 2016; Uzun & Zencir, 2021) and at a high level compared to other groups (Elciyar & Taşçı, 2017; Selvi et al., 2018). As can be seen, there are studies reporting different results in literature. In our study, it can be attributed to the fact that teachers analyse health information more accurately due to their high levels of knowledge and health literacy due to their profession.

When the cyberchondria levels of teachers were analysed according to gender variables, it was determined that there was no significant difference between the groups. When the related literature was examined, it was seen that there were studies like the findings of this study (Altındaş et al., 2018; Elciyar & Taşçı, 2017; Deniz, 2020). Contrary to the findings of the study, there are studies reporting that women have higher levels of cyberchondria (Barke et al., 2016; Ertuş et al., 2020; Patanapu et al., 2022; White & Horvitz, 2009). In a study conducted with academicians, it was found that the cyberchondria level of men was higher than that of women (Özyıldız & Alkan, 2022). When the literature is examined, it is seen that different results are obtained in different studies. As a result, it can be said that gender variables

do not make a difference in terms of cyberchondria level in this study conducted with the participation of teachers. In the study, no difference was found in terms of cyberchondria level according to the marital status variable of the teachers. Similarly, it was observed in the literature that marital status did not make a difference in terms of cyberchondria (Altındış et al., 2018; Deniz, 2020; Güleşen & Beydağ, 2020; Uzun, 2016; Özyıldız & Alkan, 2022). As a contrary finding, in different studies, the cyberchondria levels of single individuals were found to be significantly higher than those of married individuals (Doğanyığıt & Keçeligil, 2022; Mansur & Cığerci, 2022). As a result, it is seen that the findings of the studies in the literature and the findings of this study mostly overlap. According to the results of the study, it can be said that the marital status of the individuals does not make a significant difference in terms of cyberchondria. The reason for this may be that people's concerns about their health are more related to genetic factors and past health experiences.

It was determined that the cyberchondria levels of teachers did not show a significant difference according to the educational status variable. In the studies conducted by Doğanyığıt and Keçeligil (2022) and Altındış et al. (2018), which support the finding, no significant difference was found in terms of educational status. In a study, a different finding was that cyberchondria scores were found to be significantly lower in individuals with bachelor's and master's degrees (Deniz, 2020). In another study, it was stated that higher education level had a positive effect on cyberchondria (Başoğlu, 2018). The findings of the study show that the level of education does not make a difference in terms of teachers' cyberchondria levels. Another finding of the study was that the cyberchondria level of the teachers did not change according to having children. When the literature is examined, it is seen that parents, especially female parents, show continuous health information-seeking behaviours not for themselves but for their family (Gray et al., 2002). It was stated that this situation would negatively affect the level of cyberchondria (Uzun, 2016). At the beginning of the study, it was predicted that individuals who were parents would have a higher level of cyberchondria than individuals who were not parents. The reason for this was assumed to be that even if the person did not do any research for himself/herself, he/she could do more research on the internet about his/her health conditions by worrying about his/her children. However, according to the findings obtained, it can be said that the status of being a parent does not have a significant effect on the cyberchondria levels of teachers. In terms of having a chronic disease, when the cyberchondria levels of teachers were examined, it was seen that there was no significant difference between the teacher groups. When the literature was examined, studies showing similar results with the findings of the study were found (Kalmaz & Temel, 2024; Juan et al., 2016; Altındış et al., 2018). However, when the literature was examined, studies that found that the total cyberchondria levels of individuals without chronic diseases were higher were also found (Altındış et al., 2018; Tarhan et al., 2021; Tüter, 2019). In addition, in a study conducted on students among the studies in the relevant literature, it was stated that health problems were effective on cyberchondria (Batu et al., 2018). As can be seen, there are studies reporting different results. While the expected result in this study was that teachers with health problems had higher cyberchondria levels, the presence or absence of health problems did not make a difference in terms of cyberchondria in this study.

Finally, the cyberchondria level of teachers was analysed in terms of the technological device preferred for the internet and the purpose of using the internet. According to the findings, no significant difference was found in terms of cyberchondria in terms of both variables. When the related literature was examined, no study was found on cyberchondria, preferred technological devices, or the purpose of internet use. However, in a study in the literature, it was mentioned that the level of cyberchondria increased in individuals who constantly use technological devices and spend time on them (Deniz, 2020). In another study, it was observed that internet addiction had positive and significant effects on cyberchondria (Doğan et al., 2021). In the study, it was thought that people would be able to make health searches from anywhere at any time, and their cyberchondria levels would increase due to the fact that smartphones are constantly carried with people, but the results showed that there was no relationship between cyberchondria, and the device preferred for the internet. In addition, it is seen that the purpose of internet use by the teachers does not make a difference in terms of cyberchondria.

In this study, it was found that teachers' cyberchondria levels were below average and did not show a significant difference in terms of various demographic and technology-related variables such as gender, marital status, having a chronic disease, being a parent, educational status, purpose of using the internet, and the device used to access the internet. This finding shows that the cyberchondria tendency may occur independently of the demographic characteristics of individuals. Teachers, one of the most important stakeholders in education, are at risk of encountering online content that may cause misinformation and anxiety while searching for health-related information. This situation may negatively affect teachers' professional performance and personal quality of life. Therefore, educational institutions should organize professional development programs aimed at increasing teachers' digital health literacy and developing strategies to help them cope with cyberchondria. From an academic point of view, it is recommended that the number of participants be increased, and repeated studies be conducted with teachers. In addition, the relationship between teachers' use of technology and cyberchondria should be examined in more depth. Finally, in terms of e-health literacy, experimental studies with experimental and control groups can be conducted to examine the effects of cyberchondria.

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